

Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy

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**“Virtual Patient Simulators as a Pilot of eHealth Introduction
in Medical Curricula”**

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Type: Oral Presentation

**“The impact of the Self-Reflection on the Identification
Learning needs of the Medical Students during preclinical
years”**

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Virtual Patient Simulators as a Pilot of eHealth Introduction in Medical Curricula

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Background

With the continuing rise of COVID-19 cases, medical students were forced to halt patient encounters in hospital settings. An exploratory study was done to determine if virtual patient simulator platforms could bring partial solutions to patient communication. Eager to develop their clinical knowledge and skills, medical students and supervising professors demonstrated enthusiasm for the innovative supplementary tools in non-hospital teachings and introduction of eHealth elements in medical curricula.

Summary Of Work

Two programs were selected with a total of 150 virtual patients available for 3 months. 120 CyberPatient cases and 30 Body Interact cases were accessible to 10 professors and 184 medical students of semesters V-XII. The virtual simulators were introduced to both in face-to-face and online class formats, under the supervision of the professors. Instruments for feedback collection included mini-questionnaires sent to students, interviews with professors and conducted observations of interactive lessons.

Summary Of Results

Virtual patient simulator platforms were positively evaluated, as motivation and enthusiasm were displayed by both participant students and professors. CyberPatient excelled at history taking and clinical reasoning aspects, while Body Interact was superior in performing physical examination and management for acute medical cases. Barriers were identified when introduced to international treatment guidelines that did not directly align with Georgian protocols. Therapeutic options were found too specific, as alternative medication dosing and drug interactions posed drawbacks. Despite the presented obstacles, 100% of professors expressed their desire to continue utilising virtual patient simulators as supplementary interactive teaching approaches.

Discussion And Conclusion

Virtual patient simulators could be prospective extensions to standard education curricula, aiding in the development of clinical reasoning and skill expansion in non-hospital settings and introduction of eHealth elements. Adaptation of content and protocols is needed for further implementation in the programme.

Take Home Messages

The COVID-19 pandemic is a challenge for classical performance of learning process at medical school and presents a demand and possibility of eHealth introduction in medical curricula.

ePoster On Demand – Teaching and Learning

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The impact of the Self-Reflection on the identification learning needs of the Medical Students during preclinical years (2690)

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ABSTRACT

Background: Reflective ability is one of the main aspects of Medical Professionalism. Self-Reflection enables students to learn from experience and to achieve program competencies, especially related to Professionalism, including Life-Long Learning. Medical Academy is in the process of piloting Self-Reflection as a mandatory part of Students Portfolio.

Study aimed to find out the impact of the Self-Reflection on the identification learning needs of the medical students during preclinical years.

Summary of Work: 65 medical students (III semester) were involved in the study. They had to reflect on the strong and the weaker points in their performance during the assignments. For reflective writing students used the cycle of Gibbs and were guided by the Portfolio Mentors.

Mixed qualitative and quantitative approaches were applied, structured oral interviews were performed, a questionnaire with five-point unipolar response was filled by the students. The number of participants in the survey – 52 (80%), from a total number of 65.

Summary of Results: In 86,53% (n=45) of students Self-Reflection forces them to think about the need to acquire more knowledge and skills. The percentage of more positive, more negative and neutral responses for the need to acquire more knowledge to deal with the same situation in the future were 50% (n=26), 28,84% (n=15), 21,15% (n=11) respectively. The similar trend found for the need to acquire more skills – 48% (n=25), 30,77% (n=16), 21,15%(n=11). 90,38%(n=47) of the students think that the implementation of the Self-Reflection in the framework of Portfolio is important, but only 32,69%(n=17) will write self-reflection, if it would not be mandatory. Overall, students emphasized that self-reflection helped them in understanding their skills and knowledge 64,71%(n=33), in application of knowledge into the practice 56,86%(n=29), in effective management of learning process 29,41%(n=15) and improvement of academic performance (15,69% n=8).

Discussion and Conclusions: Self-Reflection helps students to identify the learning needs during preclinical years. Results will facilitate the determination of possibilities for further implementation of the Self- Reflection, as a mandatory part of Portfolio in Curriculum.

Take-home Messages: Reflection is an essential activity that doctors use in their daily practice. It is important to support medical students in developing this important skill early, from the preclinical years.